

DIELECTRIC AND THERMAL-PROPERTIES OF POLYVINYLIDENE FLUORIDE COMPOSITES FILLED WITH SURFACE-FUNCTIONALIZED REDUCED GRAPHENE OXIDE

Weihui Zhu, Jing Ma, Xi Nan, Jianqiang Liu, Wen Qin and Yongzhen Yang

School of Material Science and Engineering, Taiyuan University of Technology
Taiyuan 030024, China

Keywords: Reduced graphene oxide, Dispersants, Functionalization, Dielectric properties

ABSTRACT

The dielectric and thermal properties of surface-functionalized reduced graphene oxide /poly(vinylidene fluoride) (FRGO/PVDF) nanocomposites were investigated. Polyimide (PI) and polyaniline (PANI) are remarkably promising polymers applied to chemical sensors, dielectric materials due to good electrical conductivity and dielectric properties. So the dispersants (PI and PANI) were used to modify RGO via in-situ polymerization to inhibit the aggregation of RGO and improve dielectric properties of the composites. The functionalization of RGO was characterized by Fourier transform infrared (FT-IR) and X-ray diffraction (XRD). The light optional microscope (LOM) was used to evaluate the dispersion of FRGO within the PVDF matrix. The dielectric properties of PVDF and PVDF composites were tested by dielectric impedance spectrometer. The thermal properties of PVDF and the composites were performed by thermo gravimetric analysis (TGA) and dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA). Through the above study, the availability of the composites which possess relatively high dielectric constant, low dielectric loss and good thermal stability were explored.

1 INTRODUCTION

One of the crucial merits of nanocomposites with reinforcing nanoscale components is the ability to have high performance, including mechanical, thermal, and electric properties. Graphene has been proved to be an efficient filler to significantly improve the physical properties of composites due to its unique structure. It is a two-dimensional structure material of carbon sheet, arranged by the carbon atoms tightly packed into hexagonal lattice. A single defect-free graphene layer normally has large specific surface area (theoretically calculated value, $\sim 2630 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$), Young's modulus ($\sim 1.0 \text{ TPa}$), excellent electrical ($\sim 10^6 \text{ S/cm}$) and thermal conductivity ($\sim 5000 \text{ W/mK}$)[1]. All these remarkable properties make this material an ideal candidate for many applications, especially enhancement in polymer composites. Reduced graphene oxide (RGO) was obtained from reducing graphene oxide (GO). GO is an electrically insulating material owing to its destroyed sp^2 structure. After the reduction of the GO component, which results in tighter interlayer spacing and strong π - π interactions[2]. RGO

has good potential for capacitor, sensor and other fields.

Among the common organic polymers, Polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) is an excellent polymer material with high dielectric constant, low dielectric loss, and good chemical stability. PVDF is a semi-crystalline polymer, with the crystallinity of around 50%, molecular weight of around 40-60 million[3]. Depending on the discrepant crystallization conditions, PVDF has four different crystal phases, α -, β -, γ and δ phases, respectively. The most common crystal phases of PVDF molecules are nonpolar α -phase and polar β -phase. β -phased PVDF has a high dielectric constant owing to its large spontaneous polarization strength, which is the major contribution for excellent ferroelectricity, piezoelectricity and pyroelectricity. Studies have shown that carbon nanofillers dispersed in PVDF can induce α -phase PVDF turned into β -phase[4]. Moreover, this combination of carbon material and PVDF contributes to enhancement of dielectric properties of PVDF. It is likely to provide an access to new technological applications.

However, on account of the strong van der Waals force among single graphene, the agglomeration of RGO became the primary challenge in real application. The poor dispersion between RGO and PVDF may lead to degrade performance of the composites, which discarded essential characteristics of the composite materials. To tackle the barrier, non-covalent functionalization method[1, 5] based on holding its original structure was adopted extensively. This way carried out mainly at the presence of the surfactants. In the search for advanced matrices and an effective functionalization of complementary dispersants beyond those explored to date, we focus on new material to replace common surfactants in the process of modifying RGO. Generally, macromolecule played the role of matrix in the composites due to its distinct properties. It was known that polyaniline (PANI) is one of the most important conducting polymers due to its facile synthesis, excellent environmental stability and good electrochemical activity[6]. In addition, polyimide (PI) possesses very high thermal stability, excellent mechanical properties, and unique dielectric properties[7]. In view of these, two types of polymer (PI and PANI) were used as dispersants modified RGO to hinder agglomeration and achieve homogeneous dispersion. Simultaneously, adding the surface-functionalized reduced graphene oxide into PVDF may influence the dielectric and thermal properties of nanocomposites.

Herein, we mainly studied on two aspects. Firstly, we chose two macromolecules, polyimide and polyamine (PI and PANI) as dispersants to functionalize RGO via in-situ polymerization. Furthermore, Light optical microscope (LOM) was employed to explore the dispersion of functionalized RGO in PVDF composites. In addition, the dielectric and thermal properties by combining surface-functionalized RGO fillers with PVDF were investigated. Specially, the dielectric constant and dielectric loss were analyzed thoroughly.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1. Material

Natural flake graphite powders Natural flake graphite powders (325 mesh, 99%) were purchased from Qingdao Dasheng Co. Ltd., China. Concentrate sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4 , 98%), sodium hydroxide (NaOH, 96%), hydrochloric acid (HCl, 37%), hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2 , 30%), sodium nitrate ($NaNO_3$, 99%) potassium permanganate ($KMnO_4$, 99%), ammonium persulfate (APS, 98%)

N,N-dimethylformamide (DMF), and ethyl alcohol (CH₃CH₂OH) were supplied by Tianjin Kemiou Chemical Reagent Co., Ltd. Aniline (An, 99.5%) was purchased from Tianjin Yongda Chemical Reagent Co., Ltd. 4,4'-oxydianiline (ODA) and pyromellitic dianhydride (PMDA) used in this study were obtained from Aladdin Reagent. Polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF, kynar 720) was purchased from Arkema Chemical Reagent Co., Ltd, France.

2.2. Preparation of graphene oxide (GO) and reduced graphene oxide (RGO)

GO was synthesized using Hummers method[8] by the oxidation of natural flake graphite. 500 mg GO was dissolved by 500 mL of deionized water followed stirred for 10 min to obtain homogeneous dispersion. The suspension (1mg/mL) was sonicated at 150 W for 30 min by a SONICS VCX800 ultrasonicator (Changzhou, China). Then the mixture was heated up to 90 °C and the pH value was adjusted to around 7-8 with ammonia. After that, 3 mL hydrazine hydrate was added into the mixture to reduce GO and the suspension was stirred for 2 h. The hydrazine-reduced GO (RGO) was filtered, washed with water, and finally dried at 60 °C for 12 h.

2.3. Synthesis functionalized RGO via in-situ polymerization

2.3.1. Synthesis PANI/RGO

The process of preparing PANI modified RGO is via in-situ polymerization according to the reference[9]. Briefly, GO was dispersed in deionized water and the pH was controlled at around 9 by NaOH. Simultaneously, aniline (the mass ratio of 1:1 with GO) dissolved in ethyl alcohol was added to the above solution followed by sonicating at the powder of 160 W for 10 min. Then the mixture was heated to 95 °C and kept for 10 h. Next, APS was dissolved in HCl solution. Afterwards the pH was adjusted to 7 and added APS solution (molar ratio: An/APS = 1:1) dropwise to the mixture. Henceforth, polymerization reaction lasted for 12 h in an ice bath. Through filtering, washing and drying, functionalized RGO by PANI was prepared.

2.3.2. Synthesis PI/RGO

The PI/RGO was prepared via in-situ polymerization. RGO was dispersed in DMF by virtue of ultrasonication for 2h in the presence of ODA. Then PMDA (mass ratio: ODA/PMDA=1:1.06) was then added. The mixture was stirring for 12 h at room temperature and dried in an vacuum oven at 60 °C for 12 h to obtain polymer functionalized RGO[10].

2.4. Preparation of PVDF composites

Neat PVDF, RGO/PVDF and functionalized RGO/PVDF composites were directly prepared by injection molding without solution. Specifically, 0.5 wt% RGO and functionalized RGO were added to PVDF particles to mix uniformly. Furthermore, all the specimens were prepared by an injection molding machine (TY7003, Jiang Su Tianyuan Experimental Equipment, China) with injection temperature at 170–220 °C and mold temperature at 90 °C.

2.5. Characterizations

2.5.1. Functionalization of RGO

All the specimens were characterized by X-ray scattering diffraction (XRD, Dandong Liaoning DX2700, China) and Fourier transform infrared (FTIR, Bruker tensor II Fourier-transform) to explore the functionalization of RGO. In addition, a Raman spectrometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Germany) was used to investigate the structural changes of functionalized RGO and interaction between dispersants and RGO.

2.5.2. Dispersion of RGO in solvent and polymer

First, RGO powders were sonicated in DMF for 2 min to form 2.5 µg/mL suspension. Next, the absorption of the suspension at 268 nm[11] was measured by UV-Vis spectrophotometry (UV-3200, Mapada, Shanghai) every half hour. Then the sedimentation rate (SR) of RGO and functionalized RGO in DMF was calculated. The tests lasted for 3 hours and the absorption of the suspension was counted as in turn: A1, A2 A7. The SR of RGO in the solvent was calculated as follows:

$$SR = K \left(\frac{A_{i(i=1,2,\dots,7)} - A_1}{A_1} \right) \quad (1)$$

Making the six points drawn into a line chart to obtain a slope according to the literature[12]. And the slope of the line was the final sedimentation rate (SR) of RGO in the solvent. The smaller the SR, the better dispersion of RGO in the solvent.

Light optical microscope (LOM, OLYMPPUS CX41) was employed to investigate the dispersion of functionalized RGO in the polymer. All the composites were ground to a thickness of 0.4 mm to 0.5 mm for observation.

2.5.3. Physical properties of PVDF composites

Thermo gravimetric analysis (TG 209 F3) was carried out on the composites to evaluate the thermal stability. All the samples were dried in a vacuum oven (DZF-6000, Shanghai, China) at 40 °C for 48 h. Moreover, the dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) was carried out using a Dynamic Mechanical Analyzer (NETZSCH DMA 242). All the samples were measured over a temperature range from -80 °C to 150 °C at a heating rate of 3 °C /min and at a frequency of 1 Hz. The preload force was 0.01 N, amplitude was 30 µm[13].

The dielectric properties of the cylindrical samples were tested by a dielectric impedance spectrometer concept40 (NOVOCONTROL, Germany) .with a diameter of 26 mm and thickness of 3 mm. The dielectric constant of PVDF composites was attributed to Maxwell–Wagner–Sillars (MWS) effect [4]. The elaboration of MWS as follows: while current flowed across interface between dielectric materials, free charges accumulated at the interface. The accumulation time was called relaxation time ($\tau = \epsilon/\sigma$, ϵ represents the dielectric constant and σ represents the electrical conductivity).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Functionalization of RGO

3.1.1. Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR) analysis

Figure 1: FTIR spectroscopy of RGO and functionalized RGO.

In Fig 1, there were broad peaks at 3449 cm^{-1} and 2926 cm^{-1} , which were attributed to the presence of O–H stretching vibration and C–H stretching vibration. Moreover, the peak at 1720 cm^{-1} could be assigned to carbonyl (C=O) stretching[10]. The picture showed two peaks with absorptions at 1624 cm^{-1} and 1060 cm^{-1} , corresponding to C–OH bending vibrations and C–O bonds, respectively[14]. In the spectrum of PANI-RGO, peaks at 1463 cm^{-1} was corresponded to the C=C characteristic stretching vibrations of benzenoid rings in PANI chains[15]. Meanwhile, the peaks at 1249 cm^{-1} was attributed to C=N stretching vibrations. These results revealed RGO has been functionalized successfully by PANI. There appeared a new absorption peak at 1389 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of PI-RGO, which was the stretching vibration of C–N in the imide ring[16], suggesting RGO effectively modified by PI.

3.1.2. X-ray scattering diffraction (XRD) analysis

Figure 2: XRD patterns of RGO and functionalized RGO.

The functionalization of RGO can be further confirmed by XRD analysis. For the RGO, the featured diffraction peak appeared at $2\theta = 24.5^\circ$. It is very close to the typical diffraction peak of graphite ($2\theta = 26.6^\circ$), indicating the successful reduction of GO[17]. Moreover, the peak observed at

$2\theta = 43.2^\circ$, which indicated that small amounts of unreduced GO was still present in graphite phases[16]. In the case of the PANI/RGO, a new broad peak centered at $2\theta = 20.4^\circ$ can be found in the XRD pattern, which are the characteristic of PANI. It illustrated RGO was modified successfully by PANI. In addition, there was an emblematical peak of GO at $2\theta = 10.1^\circ$, which demonstrated GO was not reduced entirely. PI modification did not produce any new peaks, but compared with RGO, the peak intensity changed, indicating the existence the interaction between PI and RGO[4].

3.1.3. Raman analysis

Figure 3: Raman spectra of pristine and functionalized RGO.

Raman spectroscopy was employed to study the structural changes of functionalized RGO in Fig 3. The obvious peaks at 1346 cm^{-1} and 1596 cm^{-1} can be attributed to the disorder structures (D band, sp^3 carbon atoms of defects and disorders) and graphite structures (G band, sp^2 carbon atoms in graphitic sheets), respectively[18]. The peak intensity ratio of D band and G band (I_D/I_G) generally used to evaluated the density of surface defects. Compared to the I_D/I_G values of RGO (1.23), the I_D/I_G ratio of PI-RGO (1.25) increased slightly, which indicating it unchanged significantly the structure integrity of graphene. The I_D/I_G of PANI-RGO (1.03) was lower than pristine RGO. This was probably due to the aromatic structure of PANI interact strongly through π -stacking, resulting an increase of localized sp^2 domains[19]. It indicated that RGO was functionalized by PANI without disturbing the structure of RGO. Moreover, it was also found the D and G characteristic peaks of RGO upshifted when PI or PANI functionalized RGO, it means a strong π - π interaction between the dispersants and RGO.

3.2. Dispersion of RGO in solvent and polymer

3.2.1. Dispersion of RGO in DMF

Sample	RGO	PI-RGO	PANI-RGO
SR	0.0100	0.0047	0.0040

Table 1: The sedimentation rate (SR) of pristine and functionalized RGO in DMF by UV-Vis spectrophotometry.

Table 2 revealed the sedimentation rate (SR) of pure and functionalized RGO in DMF. It was an effective index of dispersion of RGO in the solvent. As can be seen, three values of SR were rather small due to DMF was a advantageous solvent for RGO. The SR of RGO was small (0.0100) which meant that the dispersion of RGO was good in DMF. While RGO was functionalized by PI and PANI, the values of SR became lower (0.0047 and 0.0040), which implied that the dispersion was improved after the modification of RGO by PI and PANI in the solvent.

3.2.2. Dispersion of RGO in PVDF

Figure 4: Light optical microscope of RGO and functionalized RGO in PVDF with different magnifications.

(a and A) RGO/PVDF; (b and B) PI-RGO/PVDF; (c and C) PANI-RGO/PVDF.

The dispersion of RGO and functionalized RGO in PVDF was evaluated by light optical microscope (LOM) as shown in Fig 4. The microscopic picture, exhibited the dispersion of RGO in PVDF, where the black blocks represented agglomerated RGO and the white part was the transparent PVDF matrix. In figure (a and A), unmodified RGO in PVDF formed a few large aggregates. The size of large PVDF aggregation was up to 200-300 μm in diameter. Compared to pure RGO/PVDF, functionalized RGO composites had smaller black blocks. From figure (b and B), PI-RGO formed several aggregates around 100-150 μm . It can be seen that modified RGO by PANI in PVDF dispersed uniformly with aggregate size of about 50 μm in figure (c and C). These results revealed that the dispersion was improved and the large agglomeration of RGO was effectively hindered. In particular, the RGO was functionalized by PANI in PVDF dispersed even more homogeneously.

3.3. The thermal properties of the composites

3.3.1 Thermo gravimetric (TGA) analysis

Figure 5: Thermo gravimetric analysis of the PVDF and RGO/PVDF composites.
 (a) Weight (%) at the temperature of 100-700 °C; (b) Detail view of (a) at the temperature of 380-450 °C.

Fig 5 showed the thermal stability of PVDF composites as measured using TGA. At the temperature of 400 °C, there was about 0.2 wt% weight losses for pure PVDF. But PVDF loaded with fillers had 1.5 wt% weight losses. Compared to PVDF, it can be seen that RGO/PVDF and modified RGO/PVDF had small weight losses due to at the presence of residual DMF in the rage of 100-400 °C. In Fig 5 (b), pure PVDF started to decompose rapidly at about 403 °C, but the RGO/PVDF and functionalized RGO/PVDF appear to degrade at 413 °C, a little higher to PVDF. This might be due to RGO large aspect ratio hinders the degradation of PVDF. Besides, with the weight loss of 2%, the neat PVDF degraded at 432 °C. For its composites, they decomposed at 423 °C. The value was slightly lower than decomposition temperature of PVDF. These minor changes indicated the composites still maintained good thermal stability.

3.3.2 The dynamic mechanical (DMA) analysis

Figure 6: Dynamic mechanical analysis of the PVDF and RGO/PVDF composites.
 (a) Storage modulus; (b) Loss tangent ($\tan \delta$).

Sample	Storage modulus (GPa) at -40 °C	Tan δ_{max}	Tg (°C)
PVDF	4.10	0.11	-43.1
RGO/PVDF	4.22	0.11	-42.6
PI-RGO/PVDF	4.42	0.11	-43.3
PANI-RGO/PVDF	4.64	0.10	-42.0

Table 2: Summary of glass transition temperature (Tg) and storage modulus values of PVDF nanocomposites measured by DMA.

Analysis of storage modulus and tan δ curves has proven to be an effective tool to assess the reinforcing efficiency of RGO fillers. The storage modulus relates the ability of the material to store energy when oscillatory force is applied[20]. The loss factor (tan δ) is related to the viscosity of material. In general, the smaller the tan δ , the better the toughness of the material, the better the impact resistance. Fig 6 shows the storage modulus and tan δ as a function of temperature for the neat PVDF, RGO/PVDF and functionalized RGO/PVDF composites.

In Fig 6(a), the storage modulus for pure PVDF composites was found to be around 7 GPa at -80 °C and decreased with temperature over the temperature range (-80-150 °C) investigated. RGO/PVDF and functionalized RGO/PVDF exhibited temperature dependences similar to the neat PVDF. Furthermore, it clearly reveals that the storage modulus of the nanocomposites increases with RGO and functionalized RGO compared with pristine PVDF. The typical results were also listed in Table 2. At 40 °C, the storage modulus of PVDF was 4.10 GPa, it increased to 4.22, 4.42 and 4.64 GPa respectively after adding RGO, PI-RGO, PANI-RGO. In addition, we can draw that functionalized RGO by PI and PANI in PVDF had smaller aggregation compared with RGO/PVDF from Fig 4. We suggest that the main reason for the reinforcement by RGO fillers due to its good miscibility in the PVDF matrix leading to the results[21]. This nanoscale toughness of RGO likely results in an enhanced mechanical interlocking with the polymer chains and better adhesion[22]. It is worth noting that functionalized RGO/PVDF showed higher storage modulus. This was attributed to the improvement of dispersion of RGO in composites.

The loss factor tan δ is defined as the ratio of the loss modulus to the storage modulus, which is related to the solid structural transformation. The neat PVDF and PVDF/RGO were semi-crystallization polymers which can be viewed as two interpenetrating networks made up by the amorphous entanglement phase and the crystalline phase[23]. The tan δ peak values also determine Tg of the nanocomposites. Tg obtained from maximum value of tan δ peak of these composites was showed in Table 2. In Fig 6(b), the tan δ curve showed a peak at about -40 °C for PVDF, which corresponded to Tg of PVDF. Pure PVDF and RGO/PVDF composites displayed same value of Tg, which indicated no negative effect of thermal stability by adding to RGO. In addition, these types of nanocomposites exhibited a tan δ peak at about 100 °C. In PVDF, a high-temperature transition (α) was reported at above 80 °C and was assigned to the liberation of polymer chains in the crystalline regions. therefore, the peak could be ascribed to this transition[24].

3.4. The dielectric properties of the composites

Figure 7: Dielectric properties of the PVDF and RGO/PVDF composites.

The dielectric permittivity and loss of PVDF composites filled with RGO and functionalized RGO at room temperature were presented in Fig 7. As shown in Fig 7(a), the dielectric constant (ϵ) of all samples decreased with increasing frequency and was relatively large at low frequency ($<10^4$ Hz). It was notable that the loading RGO attributed to enhance dielectric constant of the PVDF composites. The dielectric constant of all the RGO/PVDF composites was higher than neat PVDF. At low frequency, Maxwell–Wagner–Sillars (MWS) polarization for heterogeneous systems can be used to describe the rise of dielectric constant[25]. A lot of charges were blocked at the interfaces between the filler and polymer matrix, owing to the MWS effect, which makes a remarkable contribution to the increment of the dielectric constant[26]. Furthermore, after modifying of RGO, the dielectric permittivity got even better, which indicated the dispersants chosen in our study played an important role in dielectric properties. The enhanced mechanism in dielectric constant of functionalized PVDF/RGO nanocomposites can be mainly attributed to the homogenous dispersion of GO in the PVDF matrix as well as the intrinsic properties of the dispersant. .

The dielectric loss tangent ($\tan \delta_1$) as a function of frequency for all PVDF samples was reproduced in Fig 7(b). According to most of previous researches based on the threshold theory, the high dielectric constant will be achieved near the percolation threshold by inducing polymers into nanofillers[25]. Unfortunately, this improvement of the dielectric constant runs the risk of the high dielectric loss. However, in our case, the dielectric loss of PVDF composites loading with fillers was almost unchanged compared to pure PVDF and maintained a low value from the depiction above. This indicated that the compatibility between functionalized RGO and PVDF was better and the interfacial polarization loss was smaller than pristine RGO/PVDF composites.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This paper investigated the functionalization of RGO by virtue of two types of polymer dispersants (PI and PANI) and the dielectric and thermal properties of PVDF nanocomposites. In conclusion, we have demonstrated the RGO was successfully functionalized via in-situ polymerization from the result

of FTIR and XRD. In addition, the dispersion of functionalized RGO by macromolecules in PVDF was better than RGO/PVDF through LOM, indicating the polymers improved the filler dispersion in PVDF composites. Furthermore, the TGA and DMA results showed the composites still maintained good thermal stability. What counts was not only the dielectric constant of RGO/PVDF nanocomposites were higher than neat PVDF, but also the dielectric loss of PVDF composites loading with fillers was almost unchanged compared to pure PVDF by dielectric measurement. The RGO/PVDF composites displayed enhanced dielectric properties, which would become a very promising multi-functional composite.

5. ACKNOWLEDGEMEN

This work was financially supported by a grant from “Shanxi Province Science Foundation for Youths” (Grant No. 2014021020-4), “National Natural Science Foundation of China” (Grant No.51403150), “Fund Program for the Scientific Activities of Selected Returned Overseas Professionals in Shanxi Province” and “Research Project Supported by Shanxi Scholarship Council of China” (Grant No. 2015-035).

REFERENCE

- [1]. Xuqiang Ji, Y.X., Wenling Zhang, Liang Cui, Jingquan Liu, Review of functionalization, structure and properties of graphene/polymer composite fibers, *composites*, **87**, 2016, pp. 29–45.(doi: 10.1016/j.compositesa.2016.04.011).
- [2]. Dreyer, D.R., et al., The chemistry of graphene oxide, *Chem Soc Rev*, **39**, 2010, pp. 228-40.(doi: 10.1039/b917103g).
- [3]. Aatur Rahman, M. and G.-S. Chung, Synthesis of PVDF-graphene nanocomposites and their properties, *Journal of Alloys and Compounds*, **581**, 2013, pp. 724-730.(doi: 10.1016/j.jallcom.2013.07.118).
- [4]. Ma, J., X. Nan, and J. Liu, Investigation of the dielectric, mechanical, and thermal properties of noncovalent functionalized MWCNTs/polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) composites, *Polymers for Advanced Technologies*, **28**, 2017, pp. 166-173.(doi: 10.1002/pat.3871).
- [5]. Pan, Y., H. Bao, and L. Li, Noncovalently functionalized multiwalled carbon nanotubes by chitosan-grafted reduced graphene oxide and their synergistic reinforcing effects in chitosan films, *ACS Appl Mater Interfaces*, **3**, 2011, pp. 4819-30.(doi: 10.1021/am2013135).
- [6]. Rana, U. and S. Malik, Graphene oxide/polyaniline nanostructures: transformation of 2D sheet to 1D nanotube and in situ reduction, *Chem Commun (Camb)*, **48**, 2012, pp. 10862-4.(doi: 10.1039/c2cc36052g).
- [7]. Wei-Hao Liao, S.-Y.Y., Sheng-Tsung Hsiao, Yu-Sheng Wang, Shin-Ming Li, Chen-Chi M. Ma, Hsi-Wen Tien, and Shi-Jun Zeng, Effect of Octa(aminophenyl) Polyhedral Oligomeric Silsesquioxane Functionalized Graphene Oxide on the Mechanical and Dielectric Properties of Polyimide Composites, *Applied Materials & Interfaces*, 2014, pp. 15802-15812.(doi: 10.1021/am504342j).
- [8]. Williams . Hummersjr, A.R.O., Preparation of Graphitic Oxide, *Journal of the American Chemical Society*, **80**, 1958, pp. 1399-1399.
- [9]. Chen, N., et al., In situ one-pot preparation of reduced graphene oxide/polyaniline composite for high-performance electrochemical capacitors, *Applied Surface Science*, **392**, 2017, pp.

- 71-79.(doi: 10.1016/j.apsusc.2016.07.168).
- [10]. Li, Y., et al., Polyimide/graphene composite foam sheets with ultrahigh thermostability for electromagnetic interference shielding, *RSC Adv.*, **5**, 2015, pp. 24342-24351.(doi: 10.1039/c4ra16421k).
- [11]. <Efficient_Reduction_of_Graphite_Oxide_by_Sodium_Bo.pdf>.(doi: 10.1002/adfm.200900167).
- [12]. Xi Nan, J.M., Jianqiang Liu, Jing Zhao, and Weihui Zhu, Effect of Surfactant Functionalization of Multi-walled Carbon Nanotubes on Mechanical, Electrical and Thermal Properties of Epoxy Nanocomposites, *Fibers and Polymers*, **Vol.0**, 2016, pp. 1-9.(doi: 10.1007/s12221-016-0000-0).
- [13]. Tang, X.-G., et al., The preparation, structures, and properties of poly(vinylidene fluoride)/multiwall carbon nanotubes nanocomposites, *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, **125**, 2012, pp. E592-E600.(doi: 10.1002/app.36671).
- [14]. Ziyin Lin, Y.Y., Zhuo Li, Yan Liu, Zho Li and Ching-Ping Wong, Solvent-Assisted Thermal Reduction of Graphite Oxide, *Physical Chemistry*, **114**, 2010, pp. 14819–14825.(doi: 10.1021/jp1049843).
- [15]. Wu, Q., et al., Preparation of sandwich-like ternary hierarchical nanosheets manganese dioxide/polyaniline/reduced graphene oxide as electrode material for supercapacitor, *Chemical Engineering Journal*, **304**, 2016, pp. 29-38.(doi: 10.1016/j.cej.2016.06.060).
- [16]. Hongli Yang, Z.L., Huawei Zou and Pengbo Liu, Preparation of porous polyimide/in-situ reduced graphene oxide composite films for electromagnetic interference shielding, *Polymers Advanced Technologies*, 2016.(doi: 10.1002/pat.3879).
- [17]. Xu, L.Q., et al., Reduction of graphene oxide by aniline with its concomitant oxidative polymerization, *Macromol Rapid Commun*, **32**, 2011, pp. 684-8.(doi: 10.1002/marc.201000765).
- [18]. Shao, D., et al., PANI/GO as a super adsorbent for the selective adsorption of uranium(VI), *Chemical Engineering Journal*, **255**, 2014, pp. 604-612.(doi: 10.1016/j.cej.2014.06.063).
- [19]. Maity, N., A. Mandal, and A.K. Nandi, Hierarchical nanostructured polyaniline functionalized graphene/poly(vinylidene fluoride) composites for improved dielectric performances, *Polymer*, **103**, 2016, pp. 83-97.(doi: 10.1016/j.polymer.2016.09.048).
- [20]. Mano, J.F., et al., Dynamic mechanical analysis and creep behaviour of β -PVDF films, *Materials Science and Engineering: A*, **370**, 2004, pp. 336-340.(doi: 10.1016/j.msea.2002.12.002).
- [21]. Layek, R.K., et al., Physical and mechanical properties of poly(methyl methacrylate)-functionalized graphene/poly(vinylidene fluoride) nanocomposites: Piezoelectric β polymorph formation, *Polymer*, **51**, 2010, pp. 5846-5856.(doi: 10.1016/j.polymer.2010.09.067).
- [22]. Yu, J., et al., Graphene nanocomposites based on poly(vinylidene fluoride): Structure and properties, *Polymer Composites*, **32**, 2011, pp. 1483-1491.(doi: 10.1002/pc.21106).
- [23]. Huang, L., et al., Preparation of PVDF/graphene ferroelectric composite films by in situ reduction with hydrobromic acids and their properties, *RSC Adv.*, **4**, 2014, pp. 45220-45229.(doi: 10.1039/c4ra07379g).
- [24]. Priya, L. and J.P. Jog, Poly(vinylidene fluoride)/clay nanocomposites prepared by melt intercalation: Crystallization and dynamic mechanical behavior studies, *Journal of Polymer Science Part B: Polymer Physics*, **40**, 2002, pp. 1682-1689.(doi: 10.1002/polb.10223).

- [25]. He, F., et al., High Dielectric Permittivity and Low Percolation Threshold in Nanocomposites Based on Poly(vinylidene fluoride) and Exfoliated Graphite Nanoplates, *Advanced Materials*, **21**, 2009, pp. 710-715.(doi: 10.1002/adma.200801758).
- [26]. Zhang, X.-J., et al., Fabrication of multi-functional PVDF/RGO composites via a simple thermal reduction process and their enhanced electromagnetic wave absorption and dielectric properties, *RSC Advances*, **4**, 2014, pp. 19594.(doi: 10.1039/c4ra02040e).